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Selective auditory attention decoding in bilateral cochlear implant users to music instruments

Jonas Althoff^{1,2} and Waldo Nogueira^{1,2,3,*} ¹ Department of Otolaryngology, Hannover Medical School, Hanover, Germany² Cluster of Excellence Hearing4all, Hanover, Germany³ Hearing and Neurotechnology Group, Institute of Neuroscience and the Department of Microelectronics and Systems Electronics, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: NogueiraVazquez.Waldo@mh-hannover.de**Keywords:** cochlear implant, selective auditory attention decoding, music, brain computer interface

Abstract

Objective. electroencephalography (EEG) data can be used to decode an attended sound source in normal-hearing (NH) listeners, even for music stimuli. This information could steer the sound processing strategy for cochlear implants (CIs) users, potentially improving their music listening experience. The aim of this study was to investigate whether selective auditory attention decoding (SAAD) could be performed in CI users for music stimuli. **Approach.** High-density EEG was recorded from 8 NH listeners and 8 CI users. Duets containing a clarinet and cello were dichotically presented. A linear decoder was trained to reconstruct audio features of the attended instrument from EEG data. The estimated attended instrument was selected based on which of the two instruments had a higher correlation to the reconstructed instrument. EEG recordings are challenging in CI users, as these devices introduce strong electrical artifacts. In this work we also propose a new artifact rejection technique that employs independent component analysis (ICA) to calculate independent components and to automate their selection for removal, which we termed Artifact suppression ICA. **Main results.** In this paper, we showed that it was possible to perform SAAD for music in CI users. The decoding accuracies were 59.4% for NH listeners and 59.8% for CI users with the proposed algorithm. Using the proposed algorithm, the correlation coefficients between the reconstructed audio feature and the attended audio feature were improved in conditions where the artifact was more prominent. **Significance.** The results indicate that selective auditory attention to musical instruments can be effectively decoded, and that this decoding is enhanced by the new artifact reduction algorithm, particularly in scenarios where the cochlear implant's electrical artifact has greater influence. Moreover, these results could be relevant as an objective measure of music perception or for a brain computer interface that improves music enjoyment. Additionally we showed that the stimulation artifact can be suppressed. The ethics of MHH approved this study (8874_BO_K_2020).

1. Introduction

Cochlear implants (CIs) can provide functional hearing, leading to enhanced speech intelligibility for individuals experiencing profound sensorineural hearing impairment (Krueger *et al* 2008). These devices bypass damaged hair cells and directly stimulate the auditory nerve through electrical pulses delivered by electrodes implanted in the cochlea. CIs provide

large improvements when listening to speech in quiet environments, but provide less benefit in noisy situations or when listening to music. In terms of music perception, CI users demonstrate rhythm perception comparable to normal-hearing (NH) listeners; however, they exhibit substantial difficulties in perceiving melody and timbre perception (McDermott 2004, Limb *et al* 2014, Nogueira *et al* 2019a). This effect is likely due to limitations in the number of electrodes,

the number of independent channels available, broad electrical field spread, and restricted temporal fine structure transmission in CIs. Building upon recent findings demonstrating the decoding of attentional focus to musical elements in NH listeners through electroencephalography (EEG), this work explores the research question of whether this is possible in CI users (Cantisani *et al* 2019a, Hausfeld *et al* 2021, Simon *et al* 2023).

Numerous studies have attempted to improve music perception of CI users through preprocessing algorithms to enhance certain elements of music and improve enjoyment with these devices (Buyens *et al* 2015a, Pons *et al* 2016, Tahmasebi *et al* 2020). The focus lies often on increasing the level of the singing voice (Tahmasebi *et al* 2020) or enhancing the level of bass and percussion (Buyens *et al* 2015a). Other solutions include minimizing spectral complexity of music (Nagathil *et al* 2016) or emphasizing onsets of instruments (Buyens *et al* 2015a). However, results of these studies show high variability in individual preferences when using preprocessing algorithms to enhance musical elements (Althoff *et al* 2024).

A potential approach involves offering CI users personalized auditory enhancement of specific musical elements. This could be achieved by monitoring neural activity to determine the listener's focus of attention while listening to music. The concept of identifying the listener's focus is known as selective auditory attention decoding (SAAD). It is also sometimes referred to as selective attention decoding or just auditory attention decoding.

SAAD can be performed by recording neural activity through EEG. A linear decoder is trained on band-pass-filtered EEG data to reconstruct a known audio feature of the attended sound source (O'Sullivan *et al* 2015, Crosse *et al* 2016). Commonly, the Hilbert transformation is used as an audio feature. However, (Biesmans *et al* 2017) recommended different audio features, particularly one based on processing the audio through a filterbank. This involves applying a power-law function to each sub-band and then summing across all subbands to estimate the envelope. Alternatively, other approaches have been developed that substitute the linear decoder with deep neural networks (DNNs) (Ciccarelli *et al* 2019, Das *et al* 2020, Nogueira *et al* 2020b, Jehn *et al* 2024). SAAD is frequently evaluated in two-speaker scenarios (O'Sullivan *et al* 2015, Crosse *et al* 2016), wherein one of two stories, presented by different speakers, has to be attended. In such a scenario, different studies demonstrated that it is possible to successfully decode the attended speaker in NH listeners (O'Sullivan *et al* 2015, Biesmans *et al* 2017, Simon *et al* 2023, Jehn *et al* 2024). For CI users, it has been shown that it is also possible to successfully perform SAAD

(Nogueira *et al* 2020b, Aldag *et al* 2022), even though EEG data contains a salient CI stimulation artifact.

Previous work demonstrated that EEG can effectively track distinct neural responses to musical pieces of different genres by correlating neural activity with acoustic features of the music (Di Liberto *et al* 2021, Zuk *et al* 2021a). However, the existing body of research concerning SAAD in music is comparatively sparse. (Cantisani *et al* 2019a) performed SAAD successfully by training a linear decoder on a solo presentation of instruments for NH participants. Subsequently, the attended instrument could be identified by comparing the correlation coefficients of each instrument's linear decoder even when presented within a polyphonic musical context with a novel melody. Despite achieving high decoding accuracies, a key limitation of this approach is the requirement for individual linear decoder training for each instrument. (Simon *et al* 2023) simulated a scenario for NH listeners, in which two different music pieces of different genres were played simultaneously. Using a linear decoder, they were able to successfully perform SAAD. However, decoding accuracy decreased, if the decoder was trained on music of both genres. (Hausfeld *et al* 2021) focused on solely counterpoint music pieces of two instruments (bassoon and cello) and showed successful SAAD for NH listeners using a linear decoder. It remains an open question, how efficient is SAAD in NH listeners attending to pieces with strict metrical alignment compared to pieces with different meters or to counterpoint compositions.

The current study tackles the question of the feasibility of SAAD for NH listeners and CI users in a duet music scenario. Especially if the two involved instruments were selected from the same piece and share the same metrical alignment, making it more demanding for CI users to focus on, and additionally making it more difficult to decode. For this, we dichotomically presented polyphonic music made of two instruments. We evaluated the SAAD paradigm utilizing a linear decoder with various neural and audio feature extraction methods. Also, the efficacy of different audio features and EEG band-pass-filter configurations for SAAD in CI users was investigated. Additionally, the influence of CI stimulation artifacts on the SAAD quality was evaluated and a novel CI stimulation artifact suppression method was proposed and evaluated.

2. Methods

2.1. Participants

8 bilateral CI users with Cochlear Ltd. devices (Sydney, Australia) (mean age: 62 ± 10 years) as well as 8 self-reported NH listeners (mean age: 26 ± 5 years) participated in the study. The NH group was included to assess to what extent it is possible

Table 1. Demographics of bilateral cochlear implant (CI) participants.

Participant's identifier (ID)	Sex	Age (years)	Years since last implantation
CI01	Male	75	6
CI02	Female	48	2
CI03	Male	71	15
CI04	Female	55	4
CI05	Male	63	3
CI06	Female	65	9
CI07	Female	63	5
CI08	Female	57	2

to perform SAAD to music instruments and without any influence of the CI artifact. There is, however, a difference in age across the two groups which needs to be considered when interpreting the results. All CI users were good performers as demonstrated by a speech reception threshold of less than 0 dB on each side, as measured using the Oldenburger Sentence Test. Although this measure does not consistently correlate with music perception, it is a standard clinical assessment that facilitates straightforward screening of potential participants. Demographics of the CI participants are presented in table 1.

2.2. Dataset

A dataset containing pieces played with two music instruments was generated to assess whether it is possible to perform SAAD in bilateral CI users. The dataset was designed to facilitate the discrimination of instruments. Excerpts of classical music were taken out of the Classical Archives (Classical Archives 2025), which were either duets, trios, or quartets. In the latter two cases, two of the multiple tracks were chosen. Excerpts were selected when their tracks consisted mainly only of one note at a time, i.e. no chords being played, and were playing different notes at the same time, e.g. by choosing a bass line and a melody line. Two instruments that represent two important families of classical instruments of western classical music (brass and woodwinds) were selected for the synthesis of excerpts and kept the same for the whole experiment. The MIDI files were synthesized using samples of clarinet for the higher melody and cello for the lower melody from the Kontakt library (Native Instruments, Berlin, Germany). Each track was then normalized in loudness by using Replaygain (Robinson *et al* 2013) calculated through the software FooBar2000 (Pawlowski 2022). The duration of each synthesized excerpt was two minutes.

2.3. Experimental setup

The EEG recording took place in an electromagnetically and acoustically shielded booth. A high-density continuous EEG was recorded using a SynAmps RT System with 64 electrodes mounted in a quik-cap electrode cap (Compumedics Neuroscan, Australia).

The reference electrode was placed on the tip of the nose and two additional measuring electrodes were placed on the mastoids. The sample rate was 20 kHz with an internal hardware low-pass filter of 1500 Hz. EEG electrodes with high impedance were excluded from further analysis. During the measurement, each participant was asked to sit still, keep their eyes open, and focus on a cross displayed on a screen to reduce physiological artifacts. For participants with normal hearing, the auditory stimuli were delivered through an A-10 amplification system (Pioneer Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) along with inserted earphones (E-A-RTONE Gold 3 A, 3 M, St. Paul, Minneapolis). The software Presentation (Neurobehavioral Systems, Berkeley, USA) was used to present the stimuli and was synchronized with the EEG recording computer by sending TTL triggers.

For CI users, music stimuli were presented via a TV audio streamer (Cochlear Ltd, Sydney, Australia). Stimuli were dichotically presented for both groups, i.e. one instrument on each side, and they were swapped in the second half of the experiment. Participants were asked to attend to each instrument on each side in each block of 4 excerpts (in total 8 min per block), resulting in a total recording of 32 min with attention to each of the two instruments on both sides per participant. The presentation level of the music was set to a loudness level of 6 ('comfortably loud') on a 10-point scale where '0' is inaudible and '10' is a painfully loud.

2.4. Data processing and evaluation

Recording channels with impedances higher than 100 k Ω were removed. Second-order blind identification (Belouchrani *et al* 1997) was applied to the EEG data to extract independent components (ICs), which could then be removed if containing a CI stimulation artifact. Depending on the condition, the stimulation artifact was identified visually by a drastic change in amplitude before and after the stop of stimulation. The data was downsampled to 64 Hz and processed with different analysis bandpass filters of either 2 to 8 Hz ('full band'), 0.4 to 4 Hz ('delta band'), 4 to 8 Hz ('theta band') and 8 to 13 Hz ('alpha band'). EEG data from CI users was shifted by 50 ms to account for the

delay caused by the sound transmission via the audio streamer.

The music signals were processed and different audio features were extracted, similar to the ones extracted by (Biesmans *et al* 2017). In this study, we focus on the often used envelope ('abs', see equation (1)) and the power law ('power-law', see equation (2)). Additionally, we use features based on the sum of the 'abs' or the 'power-law' across all subbands obtained from processing the music signals through a filterbank. This usage of filterbanks has been shown to increase decoding accuracies in SAAD for speech. These features are referred to as 'abs_{sub}' and 'power-law_{sub}'. The audio feature was then down-sampled to 64 Hz and a band-pass filter identical to the EEG analysis filter was applied ('full band', 'delta band', 'theta band', and 'alpha band'). Note that the band-pass filter here is applied to the extracted features, not to the raw signal.

$$F_{\text{abs}}(t) = |(\mathcal{H}(s(t)))|, \quad (1)$$

where F_{abs} is the extracted 'abs' feature with time index t , $|\cdot|$ denotes the absolute operator, \mathcal{H} the Hilbert-transform, and s the music signal. The power-law feature is defined by:

$$F_{\text{power-law}}(t) = |s(t)|^{0.6}. \quad (2)$$

The audio features involving a filterbank are defined by

$$F_{X_{\text{sub}}}(t) = \frac{1}{n_f} \cdot \sum_f F_{X,f}(t), \quad (3)$$

where X is either power-law or abs, n_f is the number of subband signals, and $F_{X,f}$ denotes an audio feature (X) on the f th subband signal.

2.5. SAAD

SAAD was analyzed using the backward model approach with the mTRF Toolbox (Crosse *et al* 2016). By using the backward model, the audio feature of the attended stimulus was reconstructed from the neural activity recordings. An overview of the experimental setup can be seen in figure 1. EEG data was then processed using Matlab (The Mathworks, Inc. Natick, Massachusetts) and the EEGLab Toolbox (Delorme *et al* 2004a). EEG recordings were split into 1 min excerpts. The reconstructed stimulus $\hat{s}(t)$ for the backward model was calculated as follows:

$$\hat{s}(t) = \sum_t \sum_{\tau} r(t + \tau, c) g(\tau, c), \quad (4)$$

where t is a time index, r is the neural response, g is the decoder, c is the channel index, and τ the corresponding lag to compensate for the processing

delay of the auditory pathway. The decoder can be calculated as:

$$g = (R^T R + \lambda I)^{-1} R^T s, \quad (5)$$

where R is the lagged time series of the response matrix r . λ is the regularization parameter, and I is the unity matrix.

In this study, the parameters lag and λ were optimized. While the lagged time series matrix was produced using a lag-window of 16 ms, we refer in the rest of this manuscript only to the start of the lag-window and call them lag for ease of reading. The lags could be in the interval of 0 to 500 ms, and λ was chosen from the following values: 1×10^{-5} , 1×10^{-3} , 1×10^{-1} , 1×10^{-3} , or 1×10^{-5} . To reduce overfitting on the dataset, a leave-one-out cross-validation was performed. Correlations were calculated between the reconstructed audio feature (see equation (4)) and the extracted audio feature as target for the attended correlation coefficient (ρ_a) and the non-target for the unattended correlation coefficient (ρ_u). If the correlation coefficient of the attended audio was larger than the unattended, a decoding trial was marked as successful. The decoding accuracy for each participant was quantified by the ratio of successful decodings to the total number of 32 trials, each lasting 1 min long.

2.6. Statistical analysis

The SAAD was statistically significant, if the mean decoding accuracy was outside of the 95% confidence interval of a random guesser modeled with a binomial distribution of probability $p = 0.5$ and population size of $n = 8$ (number of participants). This difference was evaluated at three different lags: For NH 80 ms, 272 ms, and 432 ms, and for CI users 80 ms, 224 ms, and 368 ms. These lags were chosen based on the peaks of the correlation coefficient (ρ_a) curve across lags for each group (i.e. NH and CI users). To compensate for type-I-errors due to multiple comparisons, a Holm–Bonferroni-correction was performed. Only corrected p -values are reported in this manuscript.

To evaluate the effect of the EEG analysis filter on decoding accuracy, a Friedman test was utilized. This test was applied to the mean decoding accuracies across the EEG analysis filters for each of the three evaluated lags and conditions.

To assess the effect of using broadband or subband audio features on the decoding accuracy a Wilcoxon-signed-rank test was used.

To evaluate individual parameter optimization, a Wilcoxon-signed-rank test was employed to compare the decoding accuracies between population-wide and individualized lag and regularization parameter λ .

Figure 1. An overview of the experimental setup and the post-processing. Audio features are extracted from the attended and unattended stimuli. Electroencephalography (EEG) recordings from a participant are captured and transformed via independent component analysis (ICA). Then, depending on the condition, either the independent components (ICs) containing stimulation artifact were manually rejected and then transformed back ('CI-manual-ICA') or the ICs were immediately forwarded to a linear decoder ('CI-ASICA'). This data was then lagged, and for each lag a linear decoder was trained to reconstruct the attended audio feature as a target. The correlation coefficient between the estimated audio feature and the attended or unattended audio feature was then used to classify the estimated attended source.

2.7. Artifact suppression IC analysis (ASICA).

Proposed artifact suppression method

A new algorithm was proposed to automate the rejection of ICs that contain CI stimulation artifact. In the classical approach of SAAD, a decoder was designed based on the least mean square (LMS) error between s and \hat{s} , which was estimated optimizing scalar weights for each EEG channel. In the new artifact rejection algorithm, the ICs are directly applied to the SAAD pipeline without any further adjustment, as they share the same dimensionality as the EEG data. The contribution of the electrical artifact on the ICs caused by each instrument was balanced, as the same instrument was presented equal amount of times in the attended or unattended conditions. Therefore, ICs containing stimulation artifact did not contribute in reconstructing the audio feature and received a lower scalar weight through the LMS. Therefore equation (4) was adjusted as follows:

$$\hat{s}(t) = \sum_n \sum_\tau \bar{r}(t + \tau, c) \bar{g}(\tau, c), \quad (6)$$

where \bar{r} corresponds to r in the IC domain with $\bar{r} = W_{ICA} \cdot r$ where W_{ICA} is the mixing matrix from the ICA algorithm. After applying LMS, this results in an altered version of equation (5), where the time-lagged matrix \bar{R} was replacing R :

$$\bar{g} = \left(\bar{R}^T \bar{R} + \lambda I \right)^{-1} \bar{R}^T s. \quad (7)$$

The proposed algorithm is termed 'ASICA' (artifact suppression ICA). Because we apply this algorithm to remove the CI artifacts, we refer to the condition, in which this algorithm is applied to, as 'CI-ASICA' in the remainder of this manuscript.

3. Results

This section presents the evaluation of the correlation coefficients in the 'full band' and 'delta band' analysis filters across conditions. Subsequently, the impact of the EEG analysis filter and audio feature on decoding accuracies was assessed across various conditions. Additionally, the effect of individualizing the parameter optimization for the lag and the regularization parameter λ on both correlation coefficients and decoding accuracy was examined.

3.1. Correlation coefficients across lags

3.1.1. 'Full band' EEG analysis filter

Figure 2(a) presents the correlation coefficients of SAAD across lags for the NH group using 'full band' (2 to 8 Hz) EEG analysis filter. The mean correlation coefficients across NH listeners for the attended instrument were significantly larger than those for the unattended instrument at the 272 ms ($p = 0.012$) and 432 ms ($p = 0.035$) lags.

Furthermore, we assessed SAAD in CI users, and examined the impact of the stimulation artifact and its removal. Figures 2(b)–(d) presents the correlation coefficients of SAAD across lags for the CI user group using 'full band' (2 to 8 Hz) EEG analysis filter for the three evaluated conditions. In the CI-no-ICA condition, i.e. the condition without CI stimulus artifact removal, the attended and unattended correlation coefficients were only significantly different at a lag of 368 ms ($p = 0.012$). For the CI-manual-ICA condition, ICs were manually inspected and rejected. Here, none of the evaluated lags showed a significant difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficients. In the CI-ASICA condition, both the 224 ms ($p < 0.001$) and the 368 ms

($p = 0.008$) lag showed statistically significant differences between the attended and unattended correlation coefficients. Note that the correlation coefficients at the 224 ms lag were not significantly different in the CI-no-ICA condition.

3.1.2. ‘Delta band’ EEG analysis filter

Figure 3 presents the correlation coefficients of SAAD across lags for the NH group and CI user group across the conditions using the ‘delta band’ (0.4 to 4 Hz) EEG analysis filter. For the NH group, the only significant difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficient was at the 80 ms lag ($p < 0.001$). For the CI-no-ICA, significant differences were found at the 80 ms ($p = 0.011$) and 368 ms lag ($p = 0.035$). For the CI-manual-ICA conditions significant differences were found at the 80 ms ($p = 0.011$) and 368 ms lag ($p = 0.035$).

Note however, that for the 368 ms lag in the CI-manual-ICA condition, the unattended correlation coefficient was significantly larger than the attended one. For the CI-ASICA, all three lags (lag at 80 ms: p

$= 0.035$, lag at 224 ms: $p = 0.011$, and lag at 368 ms: $p = 0.008$ respectively) were significantly different.

For a better comparison, the differences between the attended and unattended correlation coefficients are shown in figure 4 for CI-no-ICA and CI-ASICA.

3.2. Accuracies of SAAD

This section evaluates the decoding accuracies, i.e. how frequently the attended correlation coefficients were higher than the unattended ones. For this, the parameter optimization for lag and regularization parameter λ was either performed for the whole group (population wide) and condition or for each participant independently.

3.2.1. Effect of EEG analysis filter on decoding accuracy

The overall mean accuracy of the evaluated conditions (i.e. NH, CI-no-ICA, CI-manual-ICA, and CI-ASICA) in relation to the EEG analysis filter (‘full band’, ‘delta band’, and ‘theta band’) can be seen in table 2. The population-wide parameter selection

for the EEG analysis filters was evaluated by comparing the average decoding accuracy at the evaluated peaks (see figure 2). The same λ s were used as

for the correlation coefficient evaluation. Although the decoding accuracies differed across conditions, none of the differences were statistically significant

Table 2. Mean accuracy for the three selected peaks across electroencephalography (EEG) analysis filters ('full band', 'delta band', and 'theta band') and conditions. The three selected peaks are for normal hearing (NH) listeners at lags of 80 ms, 272 ms, and 432 ms and for cochlear implant (CI) users at lags of 80 ms, 224 ms, and 368 ms. The highest mean decoding accuracies per condition and peak are shown in bold. The conditions are normal-hearing (NH) listeners, CI users without artifact suppression (CI-no-ICA), CI users with manual artifact suppression (CI-manual-ICA), and CI users with proposed automated artifact suppression (CI-ASICA).

Accuracy [%]	First peak			Second peak			Third peak		
	Full	Delta	Theta	Full	Delta	Theta	Full	Delta	Theta
NH	54.7	53.5	50.0	59.4	50.8	56.3	58.2	55.1	46.1
CI-no-ICA	55.5	53.5	55.1	56.3	50	57.8	55.9	55.1	49.6
CI-manual-ICA	52.0	55.1	57.4	55.9	49.2	53.5	50.8	43.8	50.4
CI-ASICA	52.0	55.9	55.5	57.8	57.0	53.1	57.8	59.8	51.2

according to a Friedman test. The maximum decoding accuracy obtained for the NH listeners was 59.4% in the second peak (corresponding with 224 ms) using the 'full band' EEG analysis filter. The maximum for the CI users was 59.8% in the third peak using the 'delta band' EEG analysis filter in the CI-ASICA condition.

3.2.2. Effect of audio feature on decoding accuracy

Figure 5 shows the comparison of the decoding accuracies of SAAD using different audio features applied either broadband or subband. The use of the filter bank resulted in slightly higher decoding accuracies, except in the CI-manual-ICA condition. However, this difference did not reach statistical significance in any of the conditions when tested with the Wilcoxon-signed-rank test.

3.2.3. Individual parameter optimization of decoding accuracy

Additionally, figure 6 displays decoding accuracies for which the lag and the regularization parameter λ were optimized for each participant. Figure 6 presents the decoding accuracy results for the population-wide and the individualized decoders. To check for statistical significance, a Wilcoxon-signed-rank test for paired data was performed with Holm-Bonferroni correction. For NH the average decoding accuracy significantly increased from 59.8% to 71.9%, when using individualized parameter selection ($Z = 2.371$, $p = 0.036$). For CI users in the CI-no-ICA condition the decoding accuracy significantly increased from 60.5% to 74.2% ($Z = 2.527$, $p = 0.036$). In the CI-manual-ICA condition, the decoding accuracy significantly increased from 60.2% to 69.9% ($Z = 2.555$, $p = 0.044$). In the CI-ASICA condition, the decoding accuracy significantly increased from 60.9% to 73.4% ($Z = 2.371$, $p = 0.018$).

4. Discussion

In this study we investigated the possibility to decode selective attention to music instruments in NH listeners and CI users. Moreover, we investigated the effect of different CI artifact suppression algorithms on the selective attention decoding accuracy. Lastly, we

optimized the decoding accuracy by fine-tuning the decoding parameters.

The current study demonstrated that it is indeed possible to decode selective auditory attention of NH listeners in a dichotic music listening scenario. NH listeners obtained a correlation coefficient from the SAAD paradigm of up to 0.06 for the attended stream with a decoding accuracy of 59.4%. The group of CI users obtained a correlation coefficient of up to 0.04 and a decoding accuracy of 59.8%.

The decoding accuracy observed in the current study for NH listeners is lower than the reported in previous studies (Cantisani *et al* 2019a, Hausfeld *et al* 2021, Simon *et al* 2023) where values of 80% to 90% were obtained. These decoding accuracies are similar to those reported for speech stimuli in neural network-based SAAD systems, which ranged between 75% and 95% (Li *et al* 2022, Cai *et al* 2024).

Cantisani *et al* (2019a) trained linear decoders when NH listeners attended to a single instrument and using the magnitude spectrogram as the audio feature. They obtained correlation coefficients ranging from 0.2 for attended music instruments to approximately 0.1 for unattended music instruments. In contrast, our study trained linear decoders while subjects listened to two instruments simultaneously, which may explain the lower correlation coefficients observed. Simon *et al* (2023) investigated the SAAD in NH listeners using different decoders, each trained with various materials. The decoders were trained on distinct music pieces (piano and instrumental electronic music), two different speech excerpts, or combinations of speech and music. They reported a decoding accuracy of approximately 70% when the decoder was trained on the same instrument, but only 50% when trained on both piano and electronic music. These results support the idea that a more specific decoder, i.e. trained on a single instrument, can achieve higher decoding accuracies, as observed when comparing the results reported in Cantisani *et al* (2019a) with the results reported in the current study. In our study, we observed decoding accuracies of about 60% for NH listeners, which are lower than those reported by Cantisani *et al* (2019a) and Simon *et al* (2023) when trained with a single instrument. This is likely because we trained a decoder on

both clarinet and cello simultaneously. The decoding accuracy in our study was higher than that reported by Simon *et al* (2023) when trained on multiple instruments. This is noteworthy since Simon *et al* (2023) performed SAAD from two music pieces of different genres played simultaneously, which could be easier to decode than music from two instruments of the same piece. This is because two different pieces of music are rarely aligned in rhythm and beat, resulting in a more distinct envelope. Moreover, (Hausfeld *et al* 2021) demonstrated successful SAAD with counterpoint music in NH listeners, reporting correlation coefficients of 0.11 for the attended instrument and 0.10 for the unattended instrument, along with decoding accuracies of 90%. These accuracies were higher than the one reported in the present study, suggesting that overlapping instruments in meter and melody were more challenging to decode.

The current study also demonstrated the feasibility of SAAD in CI users when presenting two music instruments dichotically. In the current study, the difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficients was lower in CI users (on average 0.0048) compared to NH listeners (on average 0.006). Previous studies in CI users focused on SAAD for speech signals. Dolhopiatenko and Nogueira (2023) reported an average difference between attended and

unattended correlation coefficients of approximately 0.01 when the speech streams were presented monaurally. This difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficient was similar to the one observed in the current study for the CI-no-ICA condition at lags ranging from 300 to 400 ms. Using dichotic presentation of speech streams, Nogueira *et al* (2019, 2020b) reported a correlation coefficient difference of approximately 0.02 at longer lags for CI users.

The difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficients of these studies was higher than in the one reported in the current study. These results may be explained by differences in the audio material used in each study. In our study, the music material might be less distinct compared to the two speech streams from audiobooks utilized in the referenced studies. The more distinct material based on speech streams likely contributed to a greater difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficients. This was supported by the lower correlation coefficient of -0.002 between the two speech streams used in the previous studies in comparison to the correlation coefficient of 0.22 between the two music instruments used in the current study. It was expected that music may be more difficult to decode than speech, especially in CI

users. On the one hand, the primary aim of sound processors is speech processing, and CI users often reported challenges in music perception (Limb *et al* 2014). Consequently, it can be argued that CI users might find it easier to focus on a speech stream than on a musical instrument playing a melody, which could be reflected in less pronounced EEG features. Additionally, Zuk *et al* (2021a) investigated the differences of envelope reconstruction of speech and music using principal component analysis and basis spline transformation. They showed that the power spectra of the envelopes of speech stimuli were higher than those of the music envelopes. On the other hand, two different speech streams seemed to be more distinct than two music streams. Using the music material of the current study and assuming a theoretical ideal decoder, where the reconstructed sound envelope is exactly equal to the envelope of the attended instrument, the correlation coefficient between the reconstructed envelope and the envelope of the unattended instrument would be 0.22 whereas for speech material would be -0.002 . Therefore, it could be expected that the difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficient is greater for speech material than for the music material used in the current study.

In terms of accuracy of SAAD, in the current study, we observed for CI users a decoding accuracy of 58% and for NH listeners a decoding accuracy of 59%. The accuracies were also similar to the ones reported in previous studies in CI users, despite the potentially more challenging nature of the music stimuli. Nogueira *et al* (2019) reported a decoding accuracy of about 62% for CI users attending to a speech stream. Jehn *et al* (2024) reported a decoding accuracy of about 60% for a linear decoder and 70% for a convolutional neural network in CI users.

In conclusion, the present study demonstrated the ability to perform SAAD with music instruments in CI users. However, further research is needed to investigate the extent to which specific factors of the music stimuli, such as the number of instruments or the spatial panning of instruments among others influence the SAAD. Moreover, the current study showed accuracies of around 60% which may not be sufficient for a real application as a BCI, therefore novel methods for SAAD may be beneficial, for example based on DNN.

In this work, we introduced a novel artifact rejection method that employs ICA to generate ICs and automated their selection for removal inside the

linear decoder commonly utilized in SAAD. This approach that we termed CI-ASICA diverged from the conventional use of ICA, which requires manual inspection of all ICs to classify them as either artifacts or non-artifacts. The novel approach led to decreased correlation coefficients at shorter lags in which the CI artifact typically predominates.

Several studies (Hofmann *et al* 2010, Gransier *et al* 2016, Deprez *et al* 2017) proposed artifact rejection methods that require no manual intervention. These methods use artifact-free intervals between electric stimulation to record neural activity. However, this is only possible at low stimulation rates; otherwise, the stimulation artifacts would overlap, leaving no artifact-free interval. These methods might be inappropriate for music scenarios such as the one presented in this study as the stimulation is continuous. A study by Somers *et al* (2019) solved this problem for continuous sound presentation by implementing a pause of CI stimulation every 25 ms combined with an interpolation-type suppression. However, this approach led to worsened sound quality perception and therefore would not be suited to improve music perception in CI users.

To our knowledge, the proposed algorithm is the only unsupervised artifact suppression method applicable to SAAD which does not alter the input stimulus. Additionally, the CI-ASICA algorithm could be employed to reduce artifacts from other sources, such as eye blinks, movement, or other interferences. However, the algorithm has limitations, as it requires balanced material to train the decoder across both attended and unattended sounds. For instance, CI-ASICA is unlikely to be effective in neural tracking paradigms with single audio streams.

Our study showed that it is possible to decode selective auditory attention above chance level even for short lags of about 300 ms in NH listeners. For CI users, in contrast, the attended and unattended correlation coefficients were similar at short lags up to 250 ms and only differed significantly at longer lags (beyond 300 ms), probably caused by the dominance of the artifact at short lags. These results have been also reported in previous studies using speech signals, where attended and unattended correlation coefficients at shorter lags were smeared by the CI stimulation artifact (Nogueira *et al* 2019, 2020b).

CI stimulation artifact reduction was successful for both manual (CI-manual-ICA) and automatic (CI-ASICA) modes, as demonstrated with an increased difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficients at shorter lags, even though the decoding accuracies yield no statistically significant gain. At longer lags, the artifact reduction methods (CI-manual-ICA or CI-ASICA) did not have a strong effect on the difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficients, probably because the stimulation artifact has a lesser influence in this interval. Furthermore, the proposed ASICA

algorithm enhanced the difference between the attended and unattended correlation coefficients in comparison to CI-manual-ICA, especially at short lags where more influence of the CI the artifact is expected. This may indicate that CI-ASICA may keep more neural signals than CI-manual-ICA. The proposed ASICA algorithm resulted in an increased decoding accuracy, although this improvement did not reach statistical significance. Conversely, manual suppression actually decreased the decoding accuracy, although without statistical significance. This may be explained by the fact that the highest accuracy for SAAD is obtained at a longer lag, in a lag interval where the stimulation artifact does not have a strong effect anyway. However, manual removal of the stimulation artifacts is likely to also eliminate some neural activity, which could be detrimental to SAAD.

We hypothesized that training the mixing matrix in the ASICA algorithm requires a balanced dataset. However, further investigation is necessary to assess the extent to which the mixing matrix generalizes and to determine the required degree of balance in the dataset in the training that leads to successful SAAD.

In the current study, the lag and λ parameters were individually optimized for each NH listener and CI user. The rationale for individually optimizing these parameters was to account for subject-specific factors. The lag parameter is strongly influenced by the latency of the auditory pathway, which can vary significantly across participants. Similarly, the λ parameter may reflect differences in EEG montage and the impact of electrical artifacts, making it subject-dependent as well.

In a realistic application scenario, these parameters could be calibrated during a dedicated training session for each participant. To incorporate this variability, we performed an individual optimization of SAAD for both parameters.

This optimization led to a higher decoding accuracy of about ten percentage points. These results reinforce earlier findings of Nogueira *et al* (2019), where individual parameters also led to an increase in decoding accuracy. However, care needs to be taken with these results as individual optimization of parameters in SAAD process can lead to overfitting.

Exploring objective measures of music perception by evaluating how music is processed in the cortex would be valuable. For instance, EEG-based neural tracking and selective attention decoding of continuous music could provide insights into music perception. Analogous objective measures using neural tracking have been suggested to predict speech understanding with acoustic and electric stimulation (Lesenfants *et al* 2019, Dolhopiatenko and Nogueira 2023).

These results are a starting point for the vision of a brain-computer interface that emphasizes musical instruments to make music more accessible to CI users based on neural feedback recorded

through EEG. This could be achieved by separating the musical sources, e.g. the instruments, from an input signal of the sound processor using deep learning algorithms (Tahmasebi *et al* 2020). Then, with the input of the decoded attention, the corresponding attended instruments could be further emphasized, similar to proposed brain–computer-interfaces that try to emphasize speech in a cocktail-party scenario (Mesgarani 2019). In the current study, we showed that it is possible to perform SAAD in music for CI users in a favorable scenario. However, further research is needed to deepen our understanding of the fundamental challenges of SAAD in everyday scenarios.

Real life music is generally more complex than the stimuli used in this feasibility study. The vast majority of music compositions involve more than two instruments that might only differ slightly in their panning. Further research is required to evaluate the decoding quality for these stimuli. It also remains an open question how high the decoding accuracy has to be in order for the sound processing to switch the emphasized instrument. In addition, real-time algorithms of both source separation and SAAD need to be developed for a practical application.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated that it is possible to decode selective auditory attention in CI users to simple music excerpts. Future research is needed to explore SAAD in more complex musical stimuli, such as compositions involving multiple instruments. It could be shown that the CI stimulation artifact affects the correlation coefficients, especially for short lags (up to 300 ms). The decoding accuracy of the groups of NH listeners and the CI users were both around 60%. A new artifact rejection technique has been proposed that employs ICA to calculate ICs and to automate their selection for removal, which we termed ASICA. The algorithm found the optimal ICs by taking them into account implicitly in the minimization process between the reconstructed and original envelope.

Consequently, the algorithm was able to achieve an automated artifact removal. On top of that, the proposed artifact suppression technique successfully increased the difference between attended and unattended correlation coefficients at short lags but not at long lags. The decoding accuracy was also improved by the novel CI stimulation artifact suppression, but this effect failed to reach statistical significance. Additionally, it could be shown, that the individualized lag and the regularization parameter λ led to a significant increase in decoding accuracy of music instruments in NH listeners and CI users. The outcomes of this study paves the way for a closed-loop brain–computer-interface using the decoded attention as input parameter for the sound processing.

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Data availability statement

The data recorded in this study is made fully available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/17639963>.

ORCID iDs

Jonas Althoff 0009-0008-7841-6213

Waldo Nogueira 0000-0001-7224-7617

References

- Aldag N, Büchner A, Lenarz T and Nogueira W 2022 Towards decoding selective attention through cochlear implant electrodes as sensors in subjects with contralateral acoustic hearing *J. Neural Eng.* **19** 016023
- Althoff J, Gajecki T and Nogueira W 2024 Remixing preferences for western instrumental classical music of bilateral cochlear implant users *Trends Hear.* **28** 1–13
- Belouchrani A, Abed-Meraim K, Cardoso J F and Moulines E 1997 A blind source separation technique using second-order statistics *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.* **45** 434–44
- Biesmans W, Das N, Francart T and Bertrand A 2017 Auditory-inspired speech envelope extraction methods for improved EEG-based auditory attention detection in a cocktail party scenario *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* **25** 402–12
- Buyens W, Van Dijk B, Wouters J and Moonen M 2015 A stereo music preprocessing scheme for cochlear implant users *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **62** 2434–42
- Cai S, Li P and Li H 2024 A bio-inspired spiking attentional neural network for attentional selection in the listening brain *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw. Learn. Syst.* **35** 17387–97
- Cantiani G, Essid S and Richard G 2019 EEG-based decoding of auditory attention to a target instrument in polyphonic music *IEEE Workshop on Applications of Signal Processing to Audio and Acoustics* vol 2019 pp 80–84
- Ciccarelli G, Nolan M, Perricone J, Calamia P T, Haro S, O'Sullivan J, Mesgarani N, Quatieri T F and Smalt C J 2019 Comparison of two-talker attention decoding from EEG with nonlinear neural networks and linear methods *Sci. Rep.* **9** 1–10
- Classical Archives L 2025 Home—classical archives (available at: www.classicalarchives.com/newca/#/)
- Crosse M J, Di Liberto G M, Bednar A and Lalor E C 2016 The multivariate temporal response function (mTRF) toolbox: a MATLAB toolbox for relating neural signals to continuous stimuli *Front. Hum. Neurosci.* **10** 604
- Das N, Zegers J, Van Hamme H, Francart T and Bertrand A 2020 Linear versus deep learning methods for noisy speech separation for EEG-informed attention decoding *J. Neural Eng.* **17** 046039
- Delorme A and Makeig S 2004 EEGLAB: an open source toolbox for analysis of single-trial EEG dynamics including independent component analysis *J. Neurosci. Methods* **134** 9–21

- Deprez H, Gransier R, Hofmann M, van Wieringen A, Wouters J and Moonen M 2017 Characterization of cochlear implant artifacts in electrically evoked auditory steady-state responses *Biomed. Signal Process. Control* **31** 127–38
- Di Liberto G M, Marion G and Shamma S A 2021 Accurate decoding of imagined and heard melodies *Front. Neurosci.* **15** 673401
- Dolhopiatenko H and Nogueira W 2023 Selective attention decoding in bimodal cochlear implant users *Front. Neurosci.* **16** 1057605
- Gransier R, Deprez H, Hofmann M, Moonen M, van Wieringen A and Wouters J 2016 Auditory steady-state responses in cochlear implant users: Effect of modulation frequency and stimulation artifacts *Hear. Res.* **335** 149–60
- Hausfeld L, Disbergen N R, Valente G, Zatorre R J and Formisano E 2021 Modulating cortical instrument representations during auditory stream segregation and integration with polyphonic music *Front. Neurosci.* **15** 635937
- Hofmann M and Wouters J 2010 Electrically evoked auditory steady state responses in cochlear implant users *JARO - J. Assoc. Res. Otolaryngol.* **11** 267–82
- Jehn C, Kossmann A, Vavatzanidis N K, Hahne A, and Reichenbach T 2024 CNNs improve decoding of selective attention to speech in cochlear implant users *Authorea Preprints* <https://doi.org/10.36227/TECHRIV.171710242.23399264/V1>
- Krueger B, Joseph G, Rost U, Strauß-Schier A, Lenarz T and Buechner A 2008 Performance groups in adult cochlear implant users: speech perception results from 1984 until today *Otol. Neurotol.* **29** 509–12
- Lesenfants D, Vanthornhout J, Verschueren E, Decruy L and Francart T 2019 Predicting individual speech intelligibility from the cortical tracking of acoustic- and phonetic-level speech representations *Hear. Res.* **380** 1–9
- Li P, Cai S, Su E and Xie L 2022 A biologically inspired attention network for EEG-based auditory attention detection *IEEE Signal Process. Lett.* **29** 284–8
- Limb C J and Roy A T 2014 Technological, biological and acoustical constraints to music perception in cochlear implant users *Hear. Res.* **308** 13–26
- McDermott H J 2004 Music perception with cochlear implants: a review *Trends Amp.* **8** 49–82
- Mesgarani N 2019 Brain-controlled hearing aids for better speech perception in noisy settings *Hear. J.* **72** 10–17
- Nagathil A, Weihs C and Martin R 2016 Spectral complexity reduction of music signals for mitigating effects of cochlear hearing loss *IEEE/ACM Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.* **24** 445–58
- Nogueira W, Cosatti G, Schierholz I, Egger M, Mirkovic B and Büchner A 2020 Toward decoding selective attention from single-trial EEG data in cochlear implant users *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **67** 38–49
- Nogueira W, Dolhopiatenko H and Schierholz I 2019 Decoding selective attention in normal hearing listeners and bilateral cochlear implant users with concealed ear EEG *Front. Neurosci.* **13** 720
- Nogueira W, Nagathil A and Martin R 2019 Making music more accessible for cochlear implant listeners: recent developments *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.* **36** 115–27
- O'Sullivan J A, Power A J, Mesgarani N, Rajaram S, Foxe J J, Shinn-Cunningham B G, Slaney M, Shamma S A and Lalor E C 2015 Attentional selection in a cocktail party environment can be decoded from single-trial EEG *Cereb. Cortex* **25** 1697–706
- Pawlowski P 2022 Foobar2000 (available at: www.foobar2000.org/)
- Pons J, Janer J, Rode T and Nogueira W 2016 Remixing music using source separation algorithms to improve the musical experience of cochlear implant users *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **140** 4338–49
- Robinson D 2013 ReplayGain (available at: <https://wiki.hydrogenaud.io/index.php?title=ReplayGain>)
- Simon A, Loquet G, Ostergaard J and Bech S 2023 Cortical auditory attention decoding during music and speech listening *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* **31** 2903–11
- Somers B, Verschueren E and Francart T 2019 Neural tracking of the speech envelope in cochlear implant users *J. Neural Eng.* **16** 016003
- Tahmasebi S, Gajecki T and Nogueira W 2020 Design and evaluation of a real-time audio source separation algorithm to remix music for cochlear implant users *Front. Neurosci.* **14** 434
- Zuk N J, Murphy J W, Reilly R B and Lalor E C 2021 Envelope reconstruction of speech and music highlights stronger tracking of speech at low frequencies *PLoS Comput. Biol.* **17** 1–35